

Metadata description of AWI Bathymetry WMS layers

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Scope

This document contains a description of the metadata parameters used in the Web Map Service (WMS) layers “AWI Bathymetry Processed Multibeam Data Coverages” and “AWI Bathymetry Processed Multibeam Data Grids”¹ that were created in the context of MareHub. It does give some information on the PostgreSQL materialized view (mv), but does not give a full description of the PostgreSQL database. The descriptions are meant for data engineers/managers working with the database and users of the WMS layers.

Background

Metadata is data that provides information about other data. It allows for the easy retrieval, management, and utilization of data, thereby increasing in significance. Metadata comprises parameters that refer to a particular attribute or variable, which defines or constrains the properties of the data. In order for metadata parameters to serve as a useful reference, a few considerations must be made. These considerations can be divided into two categories: (1) those regarding the parameter itself, and (2) those regarding the value of the parameter including the data type and notation used.

With regard to the first category, it is essential to determine which parameters are important and should be included in the metadata database and products such as WMS, as well as what to name each parameter. The latter is crucial for the efficient comparison of metadata from different sources. The problem is that there is no standardization, with each group and institute using their own parameter names. Therefore, when working with metadata from different sources, it is first necessary to determine whether the same parameter name is used or if different parameter names are applied to the same attribute. For example, one repository might use the parameter name “ship”, while another uses “vessel” for the same attribute. Without standardization this problem will not be resolved. However, materialized views provide a workaround, as they can be used to map or translate the parameter names to those used by various repositories or publishers, without altering one’s own notations.

With regard to the second category, it is important to ascertain the consistency of value data types and spelling. For example, the value assigned to a particular vessel may be spelled in a variety of ways, such as “PS”, “FS Polarstern” or “Polarstern.” This problem was addressed by using standardized vocabulary wherever available. If none existed, the risk of inconsistent spelling across the database was minimized through the strategic utilization of relational database functionalities. This ensures that each name appears only once in the database and is referenced by a unique foreign key.

For the metadata related to the bathymetric data that is displayed in the above-mentioned WMS, we have created a materialized view within our database and granted AWI’s data center, that is hosting the GeoServer, “select” rights. As a result, and thanks to the data center’s automated workflow (see

¹AWI Bathymetry WMS. Available: <https://maps.awi.de/services/common/bathymetry/wms?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WMS&VERSION=1.3.0>

Konopatzky and Walter 2024), any changes to the database are immediately reflected in the WMS layers. Although our internal materialized view includes comments that describe its parameters, these comments are not visible in the “Marine Data” viewer². The following section aims to provide this information.

Software

The metadata database is hosted on an AWI server running PostgreSQL 9.6.24 with the PostGIS 2.4.9 extension. This setup enables advanced spatial data management and querying capabilities, allowing for efficient handling and analysis of geospatial data.

Parameters

Not all parameters mentioned in this chapter are visible in the viewer for every dataset. If a parameter is empty or has the value ‘Null’, it will not be displayed. Some parameters are used as additional information for other parameters and will not be displayed separately.

Date

Name (mv): date_acquisition

Type (mv): date

Example (mv): 2022-01-10

Example (viewer): 2022-01-10Z

Description: Date of the acquisition. Survey data is saved in daily files. Therefore, one coverage polygon represents the data of one day. The default format is YYYY-MM-DD, but may differ by operation system or software settings.

Longitude Minimum

Name (mv): x_min

Type (mv): numeric

Example (mv): 9.1337642

Example (viewer): 9.1337642 °

Description: In decimal degrees (EPSG:4326)³. Westernmost sounding of the processed XYZ point cloud contained in one daily file.

Longitude Maximum

Name (mv): x_max

Type (mv): numeric

Example (mv): 11.628604

Example (viewer): 11.628604 °

Description: In decimal degrees (EPSG:4326). Easternmost sounding of the processed XYZ point cloud contained in a daily file.

Latitude Minimum

Name (mv): y_min

Type (mv): numeric

Example (mv): -50.5926362

Example (viewer): -50.5926362 °

²<https://marine-data.de/viewer>

³EPSG Geodetic Parameter Dataset Code 4326 - WGS 84

Description: In decimal degrees (EPSG:4326). Southernmost sounding of the processed XYZ point cloud contained in a daily file.

Latitude Maximum

Name (mv): y_max

Type (mv): numeric

Example (mv): -46.675354

Example (viewer): -46.675354 °

Description: In decimal degrees (EPSG:4326). Northernmost sounding of the processed XYZ point cloud contained in a daily file.

Elevation Minimum

Name (mv): elevation_min

Type (mv): numeric

Example (mv): -4967.54

Example (viewer): -4967.54 m

Description: In meters. Positive up. Lowest vertical value relative to a defined height reference (see Vertical Datum). Extracted from the processed bathymetric point cloud in XYZ format and thus indicative of the deepest point collected in one daily file.

Elevation Maximum

Name (mv): elevation_max

Type (mv): numeric

Example (mv): -795.89

Example (viewer): -795.89 m

Description: In meters. Positive up. Highest vertical value relative to a defined height reference (see Vertical Datum). Extracted from the processed bathymetric point cloud in XYZ format and thus indicative of the shallowest point collected in one daily file.

Expedition

Name (mv): expedition_name

Type (mv): varchar()

Example (mv): PS128

Example (viewer): PS128

Description: Official cruise ID. Normally assigned by the platform's coordinating organization. In the example, PS stands for RV Polarstern, followed by an incremented number since expedition PS82. Before that, the Polarstern cruise IDs contained either ANT (for Antarctic) or ARK (for Arctic), followed by a roman numeral, indicating the season number, followed by another number, indicating the leg in the given season. For example, ANT-X/4 indicates the 4th leg of the 10th Antarctic season.

Alias

Name (mv): expedition_alias

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): EASI-1

Example (viewer): EASI-1

Description: Alias of the expedition. Usually chosen by the chief scientist and/or main expedition applicants respectively.

Event Name

Name (mv): event_name

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): PS134_0_Underway-13

Example (viewer): PS134_0_Underway-13

Description: Operation ID from the measurement data management system 'DSHIP' for the instrument listed under Device. Each instrument deployment during an expedition gets an unique identifier in DSHIP.

Platform

Name (mv): platform

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Polarstern

Example (viewer): Polarstern

Description: Vessel name in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection C17 'ICES Platform Codes'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Platform Type

Name (mv): platform_type

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): research vessel

Example (viewer): research vessel

Description: Vessel type in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L06 'SeaVoX Platform Categories'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Call Sign

Name (mv): platform_call_sign

Type (mv): varchar(10)

Example (mv): DBLK

Example (viewer): DBLK

Description: Call sign of vessel in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection C17 'ICES Platform Codes'. The value for the key 'callsign', under the 'definition' parameter, is displayed.

Chief Scientist

Name (mv): chief_scientist

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Dorschel, Boris

Example (viewer): Dorschel, Boris

Description: Last name and first name of the expedition's chief scientist.

Organization

Name (mv): organization

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research

Example (viewer): Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research

Description: Organization/institute of the chief scientist. The Research Organization Registry (ROR) ID is added to the entry as a hyperlink. The English name of the organization is displayed as stated in the ROR entry.

ror_id (not displayed)

Name (mv): ror_id

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <https://ror.org/032e6b942>

Description: The ROR ID of the Organization. Not displayed separately. Only in the mv in order to add it as a hyperlink to the parameter Organization.

BSH ID

Name (mv): bsh_id

Type (mv): integer

Example (mv): 20210061

Example (viewer): 20210061

Description: Cruise summary report (CSR) reference number. Assigned by the German Oceanographic Data Center (DOD) at the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency of Germany (BSH).

Research Area

Name (mv): area

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): East Antarctica

Example (viewer): East Antarctica

Description: Broad location of the research area.

Start Date

Name (mv): date_time_start

Type (mv): date

Example (mv): 2022-01-06

Example (viewer): 2022-01-06Z

Description: Start date of the expedition. The default format is YYYY-MM-DD.

Start Port

Name (mv): start_port

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Cape Town, South Africa

Example (viewer): Cape Town, South Africa

Description: Start port name, in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection C38 'SeaDataNet Ports Gazetteer'. The values of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter and for the key 'country' under the 'definition' parameter are displayed.

End Date

Name (mv): date_time_end

Type (mv): date

Example (mv): 2022-02-28

Example (viewer): 2022-02-28Z

Description: End date of the expedition. Default format is YYYY-MM-DD.

End Port

Name (mv): end_port

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Cape Town, South Africa

Example (viewer): Cape Town, South Africa

Description: End port name in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection C38 'SeaDataNet Ports Gazetteer'. The values of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter and for the key 'country' under the 'definition' parameter are displayed.

Date Acquisition

Name (mv): date_acquisition

Type (mv): date

Example (mv): 2022-01-10

Example (viewer): 2022-01-10Z

Description: See Date.

Device

Name (mv): device

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Atlas Hydrographic Hydrosweep DS 3 multibeam echo sounder

Example (viewer): Atlas Hydrographic Hydrosweep DS 3 multibeam echo sounder

Description: Explicit survey device name/model, in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L22 'SeaVoX Device Catalogue'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed. If applicable, the O2A Registry URL is added as a hyperlink.

registry_url (not displayed)

Name (mv): registry_url

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <https://registry.o2a-data.de/items/1393>

Description: O2A Registry URL of the Device. Not displayed separately. Only in the mv in order to add it as a hyperlink to the parameter Device.

File Name

Name (mv): filename

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): PS_HSDS3_20220110_PS128.xyz

Example (viewer): PS_HSDS3_20220110_PS128.xyz

Description: Name of the XYZ file that contains the accumulated processed data for one day. The filename consists of four subcomponents. The first group identifies the vessel, the second the survey instrument, the third the acquisition date and the last the expedition. These files will be made available over time, for access see the DOI - Processed Dataset parameter.

Method

Name (mv): method

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): multi-beam echosounders

Example (viewer): multi-beam echosounders

Description: Survey method/ device type, in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L05 'SeaDataNet device categories'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Positioning System

Name (mv): positioning

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Differential Global Positioning System receivers

Example (viewer): Differential Global Positioning System receivers

Description: Type of first positioning system (e.g. DGPS), in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L05 'SeaDataNet device categories'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Secondary Positioning System

Name (mv): positioning2

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Global Navigation Satellite System receivers

Example (viewer): Global Navigation Satellite System receivers

Description: Type of second positioning system (e.g. GLONASS), in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L05 'SeaDataNet device categories'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Navigation System

Name (mv): positioning_specified *Type (mv):* text

Example (mv): IxBlue Hydrins inertial navigation system

Example (viewer): IxBlue Hydrins inertial navigation system

Description: Inertial navigation system, for use in echosounder systems and in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L22 'SeaVoX Device Catalogue'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Horizontal Datum

Name (mv): horizontal_datum

Type (mv): integer

Example (mv): 4326

Example (viewer): 4326

Description: Horizontal geodetic datum of the survey data, in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L10 'SeaDataNet geographic co-ordinate reference frames'. Only the last part of the 'identifier' parameter is displayed, corresponding to the EPSG code.

Vertical Datum

Name (mv): vertical_datum

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): mean sea level

Example (viewer): mean sea level

Description: Vertical geodetic datum of survey data, in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L11 'SeaDataNet depth measurement reference planes'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Processed File Format

Name (mv): processed_format

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): XYZ ASCII

Example (viewer): XYZ ASCII

Description: File format of the processed data product, in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L24 'SeaDataNet data transport formats'. The value of the 'prefLabel' (Preferred Label) parameter is displayed.

Number of Soundings

Name (mv): soundings

Type (mv): bigint

Example (mv): 3654082

Example (viewer): 3654082

Description: Number of soundings/data points in the file.

DOI - Raw Dataset

Name (mv): doi_raw

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.949040>

Example (viewer): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.949040>

Description: DOI of the raw dataset, with a hyperlink to the data repository, if available.

License

Name (mv): restriction

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): moratorium

Example (viewer): moratorium

Description: Restriction/license of the raw dataset, in accordance with NERC vocabulary collection L08 'SeaDataNet Data Access Restriction Policies'. Shows the specific license of the raw dataset, e.g. CC-BY-4.0, if the dataset is not under moratorium.

DOI - Processed Dataset

Name (mv): doi_processed

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.954693>

Example (viewer): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.954693>

Description: DOI of the processed dataset, with a hyperlink to the data repository, if available.

Access Processed Dataset

Name (mv): access_processed

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): Contact infobathy@awi.de

Example (viewer): Contact infobathy@awi.de

Description: Only displayed if DOI - Processed Dataset is not available yet.

DOI - Gridded Dataset

Name (mv): doi_grid

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908277>

Example (viewer): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908277>

Description: DOI of the gridded data, with a hyperlink to the data repository, if available.

DOI - SVP Dataset

Name (mv): doi_svp

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.933278>

Example (viewer): <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.933278>

Description: DOI of the auxiliary sound velocity profiles (SVP), with a hyperlink to the data repository, if available. The actual SVP file that was used to calibrate the echosounder system and the bathymetric data is archived together with the raw dataset.

Cruise Report

Name (mv): cruise_report

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): https://doi.org/10.57738/bzpm_0764_2022

Example (viewer): https://doi.org/10.57738/bzpm_0764_2022

Description: DOI or handle of the cruise report.

Cruise Programme

Name (mv): cruise_programme

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <https://hdl.handle.net/10013/epic.5f6c7ebb-86be-4277-a757-175baf6d916c>

Example (viewer): <https://hdl.handle.net/10013/epic.5f6c7ebb-86be-4277-a757-175baf6d916c>

Description: Link to cruise/expedition programme.

Weekly Reports

Name (mv): weekly_reports

Type (mv): text

Example (mv): <http://hdl.handle.net/10013/epic.47579.d001>

Example (viewer): <http://hdl.handle.net/10013/epic.47579.d001>

Description: Link to weekly report, if available.

geometry

Name (mv): geometry

Type (mv): geometry(multipolygon, 4326)

Description: Field containing the coverage polygons as Well-Known Binary (WKB). The polygons are displayed in the 'AWI Bathymetry Processed Multibeam Data Coverages' layer.

objectid (not displayed)

Name (mv): objectid

Type (mv): integer

Example (mv): 12

Description: Unique ID needed for the WSF.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung)
BSH	Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency of Germany (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie)
CSR	cruise summary report
DOD	German Oceanographic Data Center (Deutsches Ozeanographisches Datenzentrum)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DSHIP	DAVIS SHIP Display
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group
mv	materialized view
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SVP	sound velocity profile
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service

References

Konopatzky, Peter, and Andreas Walter. 2024. "Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)." *O2A: Data Flow from Observations to Analysis & Archives - Spatial Data Infrastructure*. Retrieved August 14, 2024 (<https://spaces.awi.de/x/e4XIF>).